

PRESERVING THE FERTILITY OF MOUNTAIN SOILS

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Relevance of the topic. In the current period of population growth, sustainable development of agricultural production in Uzbekistan is extremely important. It is crucial to conduct research aimed at improving soil composition, creating a healthy ecological environment for all living organisms, and producing clean bio-products necessary for humanity. To solve these issues, it is first necessary to enrich the soil with humus, create conditions for it, and improve its humus state. This requires conducting research in the area to protect against erosion processes, preserve, and optimize its nutrient-water-heat-air regimes.

Increasing and maintaining soil fertility and addressing soil degradation problems are among the main pressing issues awaiting solution worldwide (3,5,6). To solve problems related to soil fertility, it is important to reveal the humus state of the soil, the microbiological processes occurring in the soil, and their interrelationships. This is because soil humus plays a crucial role in preventing various negative consequences in the soil, especially erosion. In the formation of humus, the role of flora, climate, and slopes (exposure) is enormously significant.

The strategy for the development of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030 serves to implement the tasks mentioned above¹.

The aim of studying "The decrease of humus and humus layer in soil, its exposure to wind and water erosion, and measures to combat it" is to use land rationally and protect it based on scientific principles, considering the interests of present and future generations. This especially involves enriching the soil with humus substances, increasing the thickness of the humus layer, preventing various erosion processes, and implementing appropriate measures.

Studying mountain soils in mountainous regions is very complex, as one can observe the impact of all natural factors on soil formation. Natural factors have

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an enormous influence on humus formation, particularly the thickness and types of vegetation cover, relief, soil-forming parent rocks, and climate effects are clearly visible. Humus, in turn, affects the formation of soils and all their physical, chemical, biological, and microbiological properties (7,8).

According to Russian scientists I.V. Tyurin, M.M. Kononova, S.S. Dragunov, V.V. Ponomareva, L.N. Alexandrova, and others, the composition of humus mainly consists of the following three groups of organic substances.

1. Initial substances in the composition of not yet decomposed plant and animal residues (proteins, carbohydrates, lignins, fats, etc.).
2. Intermediate products turning into humus (amino acids, hydroxy acids, phenols, monosaccharides, etc.).
3. Humus substances, which are the main specific part of humus, constitute 85-90% of the total humus composition. The first and second groups of organic substances, which are not specific to humus, make up 10-15% of the humus.

It is known that along with the formation of the humus layer, to improve the quality composition of humus, i.e., its fertility, it is necessary to reduce the degree of erosion and increase the diversity of vegetation cover.

According to data, it is recommended to use the fractional composition of humus to determine the degree of erosion in mountain soils. V.R. Volobuev also suggests using data on the group and fractional composition of humus for soil diagnostics [9].

The study of humus, the main indicator of soil fertility, has been conducted for over 150 years, and many scientific works have been created. However, there is very little precise information about the nature of humus, the structural formula of some of its components, the mechanism of soil humus formation, and its effects on soil properties and plants. The main reason for this is that humus itself is a very complex organic substance, and it is difficult to isolate it in its pure form. This is because the mineral part of the soil is strongly bound to organic substances, and methods for isolating humus substances have not yet been thoroughly studied.

The chemical composition of humus has been determined, and it differs in properties from the composition of plant residues that form humus. According to the obtained data, currently, the composition of humus substances consists of humic acids, fulvic acids, and humin (non-hydrolyzable) substances.

Soil humus and its layer are sensitive to various external factors, which can cause changes in its quantity and quality. Mountain and foothill soils have water-

resistant structures, which are directly related to humus substances. The state of the soil's water-air and heat regime, conditions of nutrient supply are also related to the quality and quantity of organic matter. Different groups of organic substances in soils (humic acids, fulvic acids, and humins) and their connection with the mineral part of the soil play a comprehensive role in plant nutrition and soil formation. From this perspective, practical and theoretical interests required the study of the qualitative and quantitative composition of organic matter in soils of eroded slopes with different exposures and slopes planted with various crop types.

If the amount of carbon in the soil composition is higher than the CO₂ emitted into the atmosphere, this means that the amount of organic matter and humus in the soil is increasing, i.e., the humification process is stronger, which is characteristic of mountain and foothill soils. Plant roots in the soil produce CO₂, and part of this CO₂ occupies soil pores due to its weight. The amount of CO₂ in the soil composition and soil solution primarily depends on pressure, moisture level, and temperature. Soil fertility should be assessed only based on the amount of humus reserves in certain soil layers.

Therefore, in the region, due to anthropogenic factors such as improper land management, unplanned grazing, loss and trampling of grass vegetation, tree cutting, and lack of awareness campaigns for tourists in recreational areas, erosion processes are accelerating. This is leading to the deterioration of the ecological condition of soils and a decrease in fertility. Improving the ecological state of soils, protecting them, and increasing their fertility - or at the very least maintaining it as it is - should be the primary duty of every citizen of the republic

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